

1 **IL17REL induction in stage IV cancer.**

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6 We compared total gene expression in the primary tumor at stage II and at stage IV in humans with head
7 and neck cancer to identify changes associated with stage IV cancer in humans. We report here
8 identification of *Il17rel* as a stage IV-activated immunologic factor in human cancer.

9 Citations

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